

A Stable Future - The importance of stable and sustainable Oddy tested materials within taxidermy.

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Taxidermy collections play a vital role in our understanding of biodiversity, evolution, population genetics and climate change. They form a large part of our natural history collections and as such their long-term preservation is imperative. Historically, taxidermy was created using natural and stable materials with examples dating back to the 16th century. However in the last 50 years, taxidermists have moved away from these materials, preferring to use new chemicals and plastic-based materials in their work for ease of application and effectiveness when creating a realistic piece. One such example is polyurethane, a very widely used material to build the form that goes under the taxidermy skin. Polyurethane is widely tested (not in the context of taxidermy) and has already shown to be unstable and unsuitable for long term use. An awareness of conservation grade materials is not still commonplace within the taxidermy community and the result of this is that many pieces of modern museum taxidermy are made with untested and potentially unstable materials.

In 2021, Taxidermist Jazmine Miles Long was awarded an Arts Council England grant to explore and experiment with conservation-grade, natural and sustainable materials for use in taxidermy manufacture. Her research has two main aims. Firstly, to understand further what modern taxidermy materials are composed of and how they deteriorate. This includes the oddy-testing of existing materials, which was undertaken by Cardiff University. The second aim is to develop new materials that are conservation-grade but still versatile and able to create a realistic piece. This paper will present all her research so far, including preliminary testing results, potential alternatives and future plans for this continued research. Through this project Jazmine aims to raise awareness within the taxidermy and museum community of the importance of best practice in creating taxidermy, not just in caring for it. It is imperative now more than ever that we look at our own practises to see where improvements can be made. Looking at the materials we use and questioning is this material stable? And is this material ethical and sustainable?

